

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

A REVIEW ONMETOPROLOL-ANTIHYPERTENSIVE β -BLOCKER WITH ADVERSE DRUG REACTION STUDY.

Vishal Bodke¹, Karishma Waghmare², Dr. Satish Pandav¹, Rutuja Kumbhar¹, Tanmayi Patil¹, Maloji Ranaware¹, Swapnil D Phalak³.

¹Konkan Gyanpeeth Rahul Dharkar college of Pharmacy and Research institute, Karjat Maharashtra, India.

²Shri D.D. Vispute College of Pharmacy and Research Center, New Panvel, Maharashtra, India.

³IES Institute of Pharmacy, IES University, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 12/01/2024

Available online

05/02/2024

Keywords

Pharmacovigilance,
Metoprolol,
ADR, Cardiovascular
diseases
Angina Pectoris etc.

ABSTRACT

Pharmacovigilance plays a key role in the health system through the evaluation, monitoring, and detection of drug interactions and their impact on humans. Therefore, drug safety requires monitoring of adverse reactions for each drug throughout its life cycle, during drug development, e.g. Pharmacovigilance deals with the detection, evaluation, understanding, and prevention of adverse effects. Metoprolol Observational studies suggest that beta-blockers may lower the risk of exacerbations and death in patients with moderate or severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), but randomized trials have not yet verified these findings. We can see Metoprolol's MOA and ADR in all of their forms. Metoprolol succinate, a BCS class I medication with a short half-life of 3–7 hours, is used to treat angina pectoris, heart attacks, and hypertension. The normal dosage is 25/50 mg three times each day. Due to the high frequency of delivery and oscillating plasma drug concentration, a sustained-release form of administration with prolonged clinical efficacy must be developed. To deliver the loading dose of the medicine in the stomach, decrease the frequency of administration, and boost the efficacy and bioavailability of the drug by delivering prolonged action, it is highly necessary to design a sustained-release bilayer.

Corresponding author

Vishal Bodke

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Konkan Gyanpeeth Rahul Dharkar College of Pharmacy and Research Institute,
Karjat Maharashtra, India.
Orcid id:-0009-0006-9342-0689/
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9342-0689>.
vishalbodke77@gmail.com.

Please cite this article in press as **Vishal Bodke et al.** A Review Onmetoprolol-Antihypertensive β -Blocker with Adverse Drug Reaction Study. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2024:14(01).

Copy right © 2024 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

A major global health issue, chronic heart failure (CHF), is linked to structural or functional changes in the myocardium caused by stimulation of adrenergic receptors and activation of the sympathetic nervous system, which result in myocardial fibrosis and remodeling. Because of their innate ability to neutralize the sympathetic over-activity linked to left ventricular dysfunction and because they naturally lower blood pressure, heart rate (HR), and contractility, beta-blockers continue to be the mainstay of treatment for patients with CHF. This lowers the mortality of CHF. A meta-analysis of randomized control trials (RCTs) demonstrating a complete decrease in deaths and heart failure-related unexpected death in patients with CHF provides additional evidence for the positive effects of beta-blockers.[1]

It functions as a xenobiotic, an antihypertensive, a beta-adrenergic antagonist, and an environmental pollutant. It is a secondary alcohol, a secondary amino molecule, an aromatic ether, and a propanolamine. Hypertension, chest pain called angina pectoris, myocardial infarction (MI), various forms of tachyarrhythmia, congestive heart failure, and migraine prevention are among the disorders for which metoprolol is prescribed. Metoprolol is additionally given off-label for anxiety disorders because of its selectivity. Metoprolol prevents β_1 adrenergic receptor from functioning in cardiomyocytes, which lowers the slope of phase 4 in the nodal action perspective (lowering Na^+ absorption) and prolongs phase 3 repolarization (slowing down K^+ release). The two main causes of atrial fibrillation, an increase in the area of the sarcoplasmic reticulum Ca^{2+} leak and spontaneous SR Ca^{2+} release, are suppressed by it.[2,3]

Human pharmacology: Metoprolol administration, either acutely or repeatedly, causes a decrease in heart rate and cardiac output in normal subjects or hypertensive patients. This effect seems to be correlated with the drug's dose and plasma concentration. Stroke volume remains constant. To compare the impact of propranolol and metoprolol on cardiac output, more research is needed. Metoprolol administered orally or intravenously in single doses quickly lowers systolic blood pressure in hypertensive and normal individuals but takes several weeks to lower diastolic blood pressure.[4]

Following oral administration, metoprolol is quickly and easily absorbed into bodily tissues. Due in part to significant hepatic first-pass elimination, which leaves 50% of the oral dose administered unabsorbed in the systemic circulation, plasma levels differ significantly between individuals. Metoprolol's wide distribution volume is indicative of its mere 11% binding to human serum albumin. Metoprolol has an elimination half-life that is independent of dosage and therapy duration, typically lasting 3 to 4 hours in most patients. Only around 3% of a dose is eliminated as unchanged medication following oral administration, and about 10% following an intravenous dose. The medication undergoes significant biotransformation and is primarily eliminated through the kidneys. There is no clinically significant activity in the metabolites. [5,6]

Therapeutic trials: Metoprolol has been demonstrated to be an effective β -adrenoceptor drug in patients with essential hypertension and angina pectoris in controlled trials. Metoprolol has proven to be more effective than placebo in every study where the two have been compared. When it comes to preventing angina pectoris and lowering blood pressure in patients with mild to moderate hypertension, metoprolol's effects are statistically identical to those of akin β -blocking doses of propranolol. Based on current data, metoprolol seems to be a useful preventative measure for angina pectoris, as supported by both subjective and objective standards. Studies contrasting multiple β -adrenoceptor blockers in mild essential hypertension have demonstrated that metoprolol's antihypertensive action and effectiveness at different dosages is comparable to that associated with different β -adrenoceptor blockers. According to available data, patients with mild moderate to serious hypertension may find that taking metoprolol twice daily reduces blood pressure just as effectively as taking it three times daily. There is some evidence that the once-daily dose helps control hypertension as well. [7,8]

Concept of Pharmacovigilance

Pharmacovigilance has been outlined by the Planet Health Organization as "The activities concerning the detection, assessment, understanding, and hindrance of adverse effects or the other attainable drug-related drawback.[9]

Objective

1. Improvement of patient care and safety in relevance to the utilization of medicines with medical and paramedical interventions remains a crucial parameter.
2. the most objectives of pharmacovigilance involve exhibiting the efficaciousness of medication by watching their adverse impact profile for several years from the laboratory to the pharmacy; trailing any forceful effects of medication rising public health and safety in relevance to the utilization of medicine; encouraging the safe.
3. Rational and efficient use of drugs; promoting understanding, education, and clinical coaching in pharmacovigilance; and effective communication to the generic public.
4. In addition, providing info to shoppers, practitioners, and regulators on the effective use of medication alongside planning programs.

Fig no 1:- Objectives of Pharmacovigilance.

Class:-Antihypertensive β Blocker.

Fig no 2:-Structure of Metoprolol.

- **IUPAC Name:** -1-[4-(2-methoxyethyl)phenoxy]-3-(propan-2-ylamino)propan-2-ol
- **Molecular Formula:**- $C_{15}H_{25}NO_3$
- **Molecular Weight:**- 267.36 g/mol.
- **XLogP3:**- 1.9
- **Melting Point:**- $120^{\circ}C$
- **Boiling Point** :- $398^{\circ}C$ (estimate)
- **Log P:**-2.15
- **Pka:**-9.56
- **Appearance:**- White crystalline powder
- **Taste:**- Bitter.
- **Solubility:**-freely soluble in water; soluble in methanol; sparingly soluble in ethanol; slightly soluble in dichloromethane and 2-propanol; practically insoluble in ethyl acetate, acetone, diethylether.[10]
- **Dose:**-25mg, 50mg, 100mg, 200mg
- **Half-Life:**-metoprolol presents a half-life of about 3-7 hours.[11]

- **Uses:-** Management for angina, heart failure, myocardial infarction, atrial fibrillation, atrial flutter, and hypertension involves metoprolol. Thyroid storm and supraventricular tachycardia are two conditions for which metoprolol is used off-label. Every metoprolol indication is related to a cardiovascular disease. These disorders are associated with several diseases affecting the heart and blood vessels. These disorders have a variety of underlying causes, including genetic predisposition, lifestyle choices like smoking, obesity, poor diet, and inactivity, as well as comorbidity with other illnesses like diabetes. Globally, cardiovascular diseases are the primary cause of death.[11-13]

Mechanism of Action

Metoprolol is an inhibitor of the beta-1-adrenergic receptor that only works on cardiac cells and has no effect on the beta-2 receptors. Without exhibiting activity toward membrane stabilization or intrinsic sympathomimetics, this inhibition reduces cardiac output through negative chronotropic and inotropic effects.[14].

Pharmacodynamics

It is commonly known that metoprolol administration causes a dose-dependent decrease in cardiac output and heart rate in healthy individuals. Reduced cardiac output, myocardial oxygen demand, and cardiac excitability are the causes of this effect. Metoprolol suppresses the rate of ventricular and atrioventricular conduction and lowers the slope of the pacemaker perspective in the event of arrhythmias.[15,16] Metoprolol treatment significantly reduced the risk of myocardial infarction and sudden cardiac death in the Metoprolol Atherosclerosis is Prevention in Hypertensive Individuals (MAPHY) trial when compared to diuretics. Furthermore, metoprolol, when given chronically following an episode of myocardial infarction, reduces death and a second stroke in 17% of the participants in clinical trials conducted in 1990.[18]

Pharmacological Effect

Metoprolol is almost entirely absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract when taken orally. Twenty minutes after intravenous and one to two hours after oral administration, the maximum serum concentration is reached. When metoprolol is given intravenously, its bioavailability is 100%; when taken orally, it is approximately 50% for the tartrate derivative and 40% for the succinate derivative.[20] Metoprolol has a volume distribution of 4.2 L/kg, according to reports. Metoprolol's unique properties enable it to pass through the blood-brain barrier, with 78% of the drug administered finding its way into the cerebrospinal fluid. Metoprolol only binds to plasma proteins to a small extent—roughly 11% of the administered dose is bound. Most of it is attached to serum albumin.[21]

Around 50% of the dose that is administered to metoprolol is metabolized by the liver during the first pass. The primary driver of metoprolol metabolism is CYP2D6 activity, with CYP3A4 activity playing a secondary role.[22] The primary metabolic processes of metoprolol are O-demethylation and hydroxylation. For patients with normal kidney function, the clearance rate is reported to be 0.8 L/min. Patients with cirrhosis experience a change in clearance rate to 0.61 L/min.[23]

Indications

Metoprolol is indicated for the treatment of Angina

Atrial fibrillation, atrial flutter, Hypertension, Tachycardia, Thyroidstorm, Cardiovascular diseases, heart failure, myocardial infarction. [24-26].

Metoprolol	Antianginal medicines	(1) Oral - Liquid: 5 mg per 5 mL; (2) Oral - Solid: 10 mg (hydrochloride); (3) Parenteral - General injections - unspecified: 5 mg per mL in 2 mL ampoule (hydrochloride)	Angina pectoris
Metoprolol	Antiarrhythmic medicines	(1) Oral - Liquid: 5 mg per 5 mL; (2) Oral - Solid: 10 mg (hydrochloride); (3) Parenteral - General injections - unspecified: 5 mg per mL in 2 mL ampoule (hydrochloride)	Cardiac arrhythmia
Metoprolol	Antihypertensive medicines	(1) Oral - Liquid: 5 mg per 5 mL; (2) Oral - Solid: 10 mg (hydrochloride); (3) Parenteral - General injections - unspecified: 5 mg per mL in 2 mL ampoule (hydrochloride)	Essential hypertension
Metoprolol	Medicines used in heart failure	(1) Oral - Liquid: 5 mg per 5 mL; (2) Oral - Solid: 10 mg (hydrochloride); (3) Parenteral - General injections - unspecified: 5 mg per mL in 2 mL ampoule (hydrochloride)	Heart failure

Metoprolol doses with various applications

Fig no 3. Metoprolol doses with various applications.

Adverse Effect

Adverse effects, especially with higher doses, include Dizziness, Unusual dreams, Drowsiness, Trouble sleeping, Fatigue, Depression, Diarrhea, and Vision problems¹⁵ [27,28]

Precautions

Metoprolol might also additionally get worse the signs and symptoms of heart failure in a few patients, who might also additionally experience chest pain or discomfort, dilated neck veins, extreme fatigue, abnormal breathing, an abnormal heartbeat, shortness of breath, swelling of the face, fingers, feet, or decreased legs, weight gain, or wheezing.[30,33]

Pregnancy and breastfeeding

Risk for the fetus has now no longer been dominated out, per being rated pregnancy class C in the United States. Metoprolol is class C in Australia, meaning that it can be suspected of causing dangerous consequences in the human fetus (however normal formations). [36,38]

It appears to be safe for breastfeeding. [40]

Drug Interaction: - Interactions Between Two Drugs:

1. Metoprolol+Aminophylline.
2. Metoprolol+Atropine. [42,43]

Contraindications

Metoprolol crosses the placenta.

Any beta-adrenergic blocker, including metoprolol, can cause myocardial ischemia and other complications if stopped suddenly.[45]

1. myocardial edema
2. ventricular irregularities
3. Hyperthyroidism
4. thyroid condition,
5. Because the medication can conceal tachycardia, metoprolol should be administered cautiously in individuals with hyperthyroidism or thyrotoxicosis.
6. Metoprolol crosses the placental barrier in pregnancy. The placenta is crossed by metoprolol.[47,48]
7. Thyroiditis

Selected Drug Consumption Report (Metoprolol)

Metoprolol is widely used in

1. Treat high blood pressure
2. Prevent future heart disease, heart attacks and strokes.
3. Prevent chest pain caused by angina.
4. Prevent migraines.

JANA HIT MEND GENRAL STORES GHATKOPAR						
Print Date	26/11/2021	User-Itemwise Sales from 01/08/21 to 26/11/21 (@ SaleRate)			Page No.	1
Code	Item Description	Packing	Qty	Loose	Value	
SUPERUSER						
AMED	55992 MET XL12.5.	15TAB	12		183.26	
AMED	56680 MET XL 25	15TAB	8		257.40	
AMED	42943 MET XL 50	15TAB	26		71.37	
AMED	42945 MET XL AM 25/5	15TAB	18		342.37	
AMED	60692 MET XL AM 50/5	15TAB	2		132.18	
AMED	60240 PROLOMET XL 12.5	15TAB	5		812.09	
AMED	67837 PROLOMET XL 25	10 TAB	22		1653.00	
			User wise subtotal		1798.67	
			FINAL TOTAL		4567.00	

Fig no – 4 Consumption Report of Metoprolol.

Adverse Drug Report of Metoprolol

Version: 1.7

SUSPECTED ADVERSE DRUG REACTION REPORTING FORM

For VOLUNTARY reporting of Adverse Drug Reactions by Healthcare Professionals

INDIAN PHARMACOPOEIA COMMISSION
(National Coordination Centre-Pharmacovigilance Programme of India)
 Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India
 Sector 23, Raj Nagar, Ghaziabad-201002

FOR AMC/NCC USE ONLY

AMC Report No. _____

Worldwide Unique No. _____

Report Type: Initial Follow up

A. PATIENT INFORMATION

1. Patient Initials RWYS B.	2. Age at time of Event or Date of Birth 01-6-1975	3. M ☒ F ☐ Other ☐	4. Weight 54 Kgs
---------------------------------------	--	--	-------------------------

B. SUSPECTED ADVERSE REACTION

5. Date of reaction started (dd/mm/yyyy) **- 10 - NOV - 2021**

6. Date of recovery (dd/mm/yyyy) **12 - NOV - 2021**

7. Describe reaction or problem
Patient suffering from Dizziness, Headache from last one day after taking a Tab. met XL 100. Patient comes to OPD for consultation. Tab met XL 100 stop for 3 days.

C. SUSPECTED MEDICATION(S)

S.No	8. Name (Brand/Generic)	Manufacturer (if known)	Batch No. / Lot No.	Exp. Date (if known)	Dose used	Route used	Frequency (OD, BD, etc.)	Therapy dates		Indication	Causality Assessment
								Date started	Date stopped		
i	Met XL 100 (metoprolol)	Ajanta	BL503	DEC 19	BD	oral	BD	10.11.21	12.11.21	Hypertension	-
ii											
iii											
iv											

S.No as per C	9. Action Taken (please tick)					10. Reaction reappeared after reintroduction (please tick)				
	Drug withdrawn	Dose increased	Dose reduced	Dose not changed	Not applicable	Unkn own	Yes	No	Effect unknown	Dose (if reintroduced)
i			☒					☒		
ii										
iii										
iv										

11. Concomitant medical product including self-medication and herbal remedies with therapy dates (Exclude those used to treat reaction)

S.No	Name (Brand/Generic)	Dose used	Route used	Frequency (OD, BD, etc.)	Therapy dates		Indication
					Date started	Date stopped	
i	Tab. Glycomet GP	1/2 80mg	oral	BD	5.10.21	-	-
ii							
iii							

Additional Information:
Dose of met XL 100 (metoprolol) Reduces for 3 days. Patient comes under control. Does not seem any rashes on body.

D. REPORTER DETAILS

16. Name and Professional Address: _____

Pin: _____ E-mail: _____

Tel. No. (with STD code): _____

Occupation: _____ Signature: _____

17. Date of this report (dd/mm/yyyy): _____

Confidentiality: The patient's identity is held in strict confidence and protected to the fullest extent. Programme staff is not expected to and will not disclose the reporter's identity in response to a request from the public. Submission of a report does not constitute an admission that medical personnel or manufacturer or the product caused or contributed to the reaction.

Fig.no5:-Adverse Drug Reaction From of Metoprolol

Hospital Visit

Fig no. 6 Hospital Visit.

- Name of Doctor:-
- **Dr. Madhuri R. Inamdar**
- Qualification:-MBBS
- How much time you working this place: -3 year
- Specialist ofdoctor:-Physician & Consultant, Cardiologist specialist

- Name of Doctor: -
- **Dr. Sambhaji Behere**
- Qualification:-MBBS
- How much time you work in this place year
- Specialist of doctor:- Physician & Consultant, Cardiologist specialist,

Patient Interview

Fig no 7- Patient Interview.

Name of patient:-**Ms. Paramjeet Kaur** Age-40, Sex-Female

1. In which condition you start the treatment?
Ans-High Blood Pressure
2. How long have you taken this Drug/medicine?
Ans-30days, MET XL50
3. Do You feel any discomfort/side effects of this drug?
Ans-No
4. Tell me about your medication history.
Ans-She has Hypertension problem last 2 years.
5. Did you suggest this treatment for another person which suffer from the same condition?
Ans-yes it's helpful
6. What other medicine do you take with this medicine?
Ans-NO

Name of patient:-

- **Ms. Pallavi Kadam**

- Age-36Sex-Female

1. In which condition you start the treatment?

Ans-high Blood Pressure and chest pain

2. How long have you taken this Drug/medicine?

Ans-from90days

3. Do You feel any discomfort/side effects of this drug?

Ans-No

4. Tell me about your medication history

Ans-he is diabetic, and he has taken Glycomet 0.5medicine for a year

5. Did you suggest this treatment for another person which suffer from the same condition?

Ans-yes it's helpful &feels good

6. What other medicine do you take with this medicine?

Ans-Zincovit tab

- Name of patient:-

- **Mr. Vishnu Dadas**

- Age-65,Sex-Male

1. In which condition you start the treatment?

Ans-Heart problem, Angina &chest pain

2. How long have you taken this Drug/medicine?

Ans-from2Year

3. Do You feel any discomfort/side effects of this drug?

Ans-No

4. Tell me about your medication history

Ans-he has Diabetics

5. Did you suggest this treatment for another person which suffer from the same condition?

Ans-yes it's helpful &feels good

6. What other medicine do you take with this medicine?

Ans-Glycomet 0.5 tab

ASSESSMENT OF ADR**Naranjo Scale**

The Naranjo Scale was created by Naranjo et al. to assess the chance that an adverse drug reaction (ADR) is caused by the drug itself rather than by other factors. A score is used to categorize probability as certain, probable, possible, or doubtful. Peer reviews frequently use the values from this algorithm to validate the accuracy of an author's conclusions about adverse drug reactions. The Naranjo Scale or Naranjo Score are other names for it.[50]

Metoprolol**Scoring**

- ≥ 9 =definite ADR
- 5-8=probable ADR
- 1-4=possible ADR
- 0=doubtful ADR. [51,52]

Due to unstable angina, the patient's BP ranged from 110/70 to 180/90 mm Hg, PR was 84 to 86 bpm, and SPO2 was 98%.[53] After using the aforementioned scales for the observed suspected ADR, the following result was obtained. The patient was given the scales, and the scores were determined by evaluating the ADR.[54,55] Based on the results obtained utilizing various standard scales, causality was confirmed. Re-challenging was skipped because, according to WHO-UMC, it is not necessary for likely medicines. The reaction was a strange form (Type-B) with a medium intensity of level 7, according to analysis. Most likely, the reaction can be avoided. 20 [56,57]

Naranjo Score of Metoprolol is =7

Fig no 8 Marketed Formulations of Metoprolol.

CONCLUSION

One of the most significant classes of cardiovascular drugs, beta-blockers is thought to be the mainstay of treatment for heart conditions like atrial fibrillation (AF) and heart failure (HF). Metoprolol is a selective beta (1)-adrenergic antagonist and one of the many beta-blockers that has been in widespread use since the 1970s. Metoprolol is the most widely used selective beta-blocker antagonist. In healthy volunteers, the beta-blocker metoprolol prevents sodium retention caused by negative pressure in the lower body despite low blood pressure. The prevention of sodium retention may be due to weakened neurohormonal responses. These effects of metoprolol on renal responses to LBNP may partially explain the beneficial effects of this drug in patients with heart failure.

When compared to genotypic NMs, CYP2D6 PMs taking metoprolol experienced a significantly higher incidence of symptomatic bradycardia. However, the study's findings regarding the main composite outcome did not reach statistical significance. Although more research is necessary to examine the effects of a larger range of CYP2D6 phenotypes, this study confirms earlier findings that metoprolol may be clinically affected by CYP2D6 phenotype. Although CYP2D6 NMs and PMs showed a statistically significant difference in bradycardia, CYP2D6 major,

REFERENCE

1. Tripathi, K. D. Essentials of Medical Pharmacology. 8th ed., Jaypee Brothers Medical, 2018. Pharmacovigilance
2. Mugoša S, Djordjević N, Djukanović N, Protić D, Bukumirić Z, Radosavljević I, Bošković A, Todorović Z. Factors affecting the development of adverse drug reactions to β -blockers in hospitalized cardiac patient population. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. 2016 Aug 2;10:1461-9. doi: 10.2147/PPA.S108579. PMID: 27536078; PMCID: PMC4977081.
3. Browne, L.H. and Graham, P.H. (2014) Good Intentions and ICU-GCP: Trial Conduct Training Needs to Go beyond the ICH-GCP Document and include the Intention-to-Treat principle. *ClinicalTrials*:11; 629-634. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1740774514542620>
4. Ohmann, C., Kuchinke, W., Canham, S., Lauritsen, J., Salas, N., Schade-Brittinger, C., et al. (2011) Standard Requirements for GCP-Compliant Data Management in Multinational Clinical Trials. *Trials*, 12, 85. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1745-6215-12>
5. Rock, E.P., Molloy, V.J. and Humphrey, J.S. (2010) GCP Data Quality. *Drug Bank Online*: <https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB06736r> Early Clinical Development. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 16, 1756-1763. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-09-3267>
6. Switula, D. (2000) Principles of Good Clinical Practice (GCP) in Clinical Research. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 6, 71-77. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11948-000-0025-7>
7. Nanjo CA, Busto U, Sellers EM. Difficulties in assessing adverse drug reactions in clinical trials. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacology Biol Psychiatry*. 1982;6:651-7. [PubMed]
8. Brogden, R. N., et al. "Metoprolol: A Review of Its Pharmacological Properties and Therapeutic Efficacy in Hypertension and Angina Pectoris." *Drugs*, vol. 14, no. 5, Nov. 1977, pp. 321-48. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-197714050-00001>
9. Switula, D. (2000) Principles of Good Clinical Practice (GCP) in Clinical Research. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 6, 71-77. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11948-000-0025-7>
10. Khan, N. "Re-Examining the Efficacy of β -Blockers for the Treatment of Hypertension: A Meta-Analysis." *Canadian Medical Association Journal*, vol. 174, no. 12, June 2006, pp. 1737-42. DOI.org (Crossref), <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.060110>.
11. Brogden, R. N., et al. "Metoprolol: A Review of Its Pharmacological Properties and Therapeutic Efficacy in Hypertension and Angina Pectoris." *Drugs*, vol. 14, no. 5, Nov. 1977, pp. 321-48. DOI, <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-197714050-00001>.
12. Benfield, Paul, et al. "Metoprolol: An Updated Review of Its Pharmacodynamic and Pharmacokinetic Properties, and Therapeutic Efficacy, in Hypertension, Ischaemic Heart Disease and Related Cardiovascular Disorders." *Drugs*, vol. 31, no. 5, May 1986, pp. 376-429. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-198631050-00002>.
13. Plosker, Greg L., and Stephen P. Clissold. "Controlled Release Metoprolol Formulations: A Review of Their Pharmacodynamic and Pharmacokinetic Properties, and Therapeutic Use in Hypertension and Ischaemic Heart Disease." *Drugs*, vol. 43, no. 3, Mar. 1992, pp. 382-414. DOI, <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-199243030-00006>.
14. Lucker, Peter, et al. "Pharmacokinetic and Pharmacodynamic Comparison of Metoprolol CR/ZOK Once Daily with Conventional Tablets Once Daily and in Divided Doses." *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, vol. 30, no. S2, Feb. 1990. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1552-4604.1990.tb03491.x>.
15. Abrahamsson, Bertil, et al. "The Relationship Between Metoprolol Plasma Concentration and Beta 1 -Blockade in Healthy Subjects: A Study on Conventional Metoprolol and Metoprolol CR/ZOK Formulations." *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, vol. 30, no. S2, Feb. 1990. DOI, <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1552-4604.1990.tb03495.x>.
16. Mosley, Scott A., et al. "A Randomized, Cross-over Trial of Metoprolol Succinate Formulations to Evaluate PK and PD End Points for Therapeutic Equivalence." *Clinical and Translational Science*, vol. 15, no. 7, July 2022, pp. 1764-75. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/cts.13294>.
17. Ripley, Toni L., and Joseph J. Saseen. " β -Blockers: A Review of Their Pharmacological and Physiological Diversity in Hypertension." *Annals of Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 48, no. 6, June 2014, pp. 723-33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1060028013519591>.
18. Dinakaran, Aishwarya, et al. "ASSESSMENT OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS ON CARDIOVASCULAR DRUGS IN HOSPITALIZED PATIENTS OF A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL – A PROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS." *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, Oct. 2022, pp. 42-46. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22159/ajpcr.2022.v15i10.45583>.
19. Trivedi, Madhav, et al. "Pharmacovigilance Study of Beta Adrenergic Receptor Antagonists in Patients Visiting Department of Medicine of a Tertiary Care Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India." *International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*, vol. 5, no. 6, Dec. 2016, pp. 2332-35. www.ijbcp.com, <https://doi.org/10.18203/2319-2003.ijbcp20164086>.
20. Joy, Sneha, et al. "Metoprolol Induced Jaundice- A Case Report." *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Health Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2022. ajphs.com, <https://doi.org/10.5530/ajphs.2022.12.14>.
21. Morris J, Dunham A. Metoprolol. [Updated 2023 Jul 10]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK532923/www.wikipedia/metoprolol/details>
22. <https://www.1mg.com/drugs/met-xl-25-tablet-307378#:~:text=Met%20XL%2025%20Tablet%20belongs,future%20heart%20attacks%2C%20and%20stroke>.
23. Vishal Bodke A Review on Study of Aceclofenac Drug by Survey and Adverse Drug Reaction Research & Review: *Drugs and Drugs Development* e-ISSN: 2582-5720 Volume-4, Issue-2 (July-December, 2022). <https://matjournals.co.in/index.php/RRDDD/article/view/1077>
24. <https://www.apollopharmacy.in/medicine/met-xl-25mg-er-tablet-20-s>

25. drugbankonline:-<https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB06736>.
26. Adverse Drug Reaction https://cdsco.gov.in/opencms/export/sites/CDSCO_WEB/Pdf-documents/Consumer_Section_PDFs/ADRRF_.
27. Nanjo CA, Busto U, Sellers EM. Difficulties in assessing adverse drug reactions in clinicaltrials. *ProgNeuropsychopharmacology BiolPsychiatry*.1982;6:651–7.[PubMed].
28. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16014046/> .conclusion
29. Vishal Bodke et al. (2023). Review on Hematinic Formulations Used in Anaemia Deficiency Disorders, Research & Review: *Drugs and Drugs Development*, 5(1), 1-6.,Volume-5, Issue-2 (July-December, 2023). <https://doi.org/10.46610/RRDDD.2023.v05i02.001>.
30. Fröhlich H, Zhao J, Täger T, Cebola R, Schellberg D, Katus HA, Grundtvig M, Hole T, Atar D, Agewall S, Frankenstein L. Carvedilol Compared With Metoprolol Succinate in the Treatment and Prognosis of Patients With Stable Chronic Heart Failure: Carvedilol or Metoprolol Evaluation Study. *Circ Heart Fail*. 2015 Sep;8(5):887-96. [PubMed]
31. Brogden RN, Heel RC, Speight TM, Avery GS. Metoprolol: a review of its pharmacological properties and therapeutic efficacy in hypertension and angina pectoris. *Drugs*. 1977 Nov;14(5):321-48. [PubMed].
32. Adverse Drug Reaction https://cdsco.gov.in/opencms/export/sites/CDSCO_WEB/Pdf-documents/Consumer_Section_PDFs/ADRRF_
33. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK548069/adrNaranjo>
34. Nanjo CA, Busto U, Sellers EM. Difficulties in assessing adverse drug reactions in clinicaltrials. *ProgNeuropsychopharmacology BiolPsychiatry*.1982;6:651–7.[PubMed]
35. Alayed, Nouf, et al. “Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) as a Cause of Hospitalization at a Government Hospital in Saudi Arabia: A Prospective Observational Study.” *Current Drug Safety*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 192–98. www.eurekaselect.com, <https://www.eurekaselect.com/article/98550>. Accessed 5 Nov. 2023.
36. Vishal Bodke et al. (2023). Review on Hematinic Formulations Used in Anaemia Deficiency Disorders, Research & Review: *Drugs and Drugs Development*, 5(1), 1-6.,Volume-5, Issue-2 (July-December, 2023) <https://doi.org/10.46610/RRDDD.2023.v05i02.001>.
37. Cheng X, Zhu M, Liu Q, Feng Z, Meng Y. Effectiveness of Metoprolol in Improving Cardiac and Motor Functions in Patients with Chronic Heart Failure: A Prospective Study. *Drug Des DevelTher*. 2020 Aug 25;14:3485-3494. doi: 10.2147/DDDT.S263026. PMID: 32921985; PMCID: PMC7457782.
38. Horyn, Mariana &Logoyda, Liliya. (2019). Methods Of Metoprolol Analysis In Drugs And Biological Fluids: Review And Suggestions. *International Journal of Medicine and Medical Research*. 5. 10.11603/IJMMR.2413-6077.2019.2.10897.
39. Metoprolol Succinate Extended-Release Tab-lets. Tablets: 25 Mg, 50 Mg, 100 Mg, and 200 Mg. NDA 19 [19962/S032:3](https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2006/019962s032lbl.pdf). Available from: https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2006/019962s032lbl.pdf. Accessed 13 Jan 2019.
40. Nazim, Sayyed & Abdul Rafique, Dr & Patel, Sawban. (2015). Formulation and Evaluation of Bilayer tablets of Metoprolol Succinate. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 8. 292. 10.5958/0974-360X.2015.00049.9.
41. Lu, Zhengwu. “Information Technology in Pharmacovigilance: Benefits, Challenges, and Future Directions from Industry Perspectives.” *Drug, Healthcare and Patient Safety*, Oct. 2009, p. 35. DOI. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DHPS.S7180>.
42. Kumar, B. N., et al. “A Pharmacovigilance Study in Medicine Department of Tertiary Care Hospital in Chhattisgarh (Jagdalpur), India.” *Journal of Young Pharmacists*, vol. 2, no. 1, Jan. 2010, pp. 95–100. DOI.org (Crossref), <https://doi.org/10.4103/0975-1483.62222>.
43. Dutta, Siddhartha, et al. “Pharmacovigilance In The Era Of Covid-19: A Concise Review Of The Current Scenario, Implications, And Challenges.” *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*, May 2021, pp. 1–4. DOI.org (Crossref), <https://doi.org/10.22159/ijap.2021v13i3.41063>.
44. Pharmacovigilante’s in the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India: Ideal Qualities and Skills | *Journal of Young Pharmacists*. 1 Apr. 2016, <https://jyoungpharm.org/article/856>.
45. Sathyaraj, A & Abhinav, K. (2012). Formulation and evaluation of metoprolol succinate controlled release tablets using natural and synthetic polymer. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 3.
46. Eugene, Andy R. “Metoprolol Dose Equivalence in Adult Men and Women Based on Gender Differences: Pharmacokinetic Modeling and Simulations.” *Medical Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 4, Dec. 2016, p. 18. www.mdpi.com, <https://doi.org/10.3390/medsci4040018>.
47. Uddin, Mohammed Baleeqh, et al. “A Case Report on Metoprolol Overdose.” *IP International Journal of Forensic Medicine and Toxicological Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 2, Aug. 2020, pp. 74–76. www.ijfmts.com, <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijfmts.2020.017>.
48. Anfinogenova, Nina D., et al. “Prescribed Versus Taken Polypharmacy and Drug–Drug Interactions in Older Cardiovascular Patients during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Observational Cross-Sectional Analytical Study.” *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, vol. 12, no. 15, Aug. 2023, p. 5061. DOI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12155061>.
49. Mathew, Eby, et al. “A Prospective Observational Study On Prescribing Trends And Adverse Drug Reactions In Stroke Patients.” *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 7, July 2017, p. 25. DOI.org (Crossref), <https://doi.org/10.22159/ijpps.2017v9i7.14189>.
50. Gholami, Kheirollah, et al. “Adverse Drug Reactions Induced by Cardiovascular Drugs in Outpatients.” *Pharmacy Practice (Internet)*, vol. 6, no. 1, Mar. 2008. DOI.org (Crossref), <https://doi.org/10.4321/S1886-36552008000100008>.
51. MedlinePlus [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): National Library of Medicine (US); [updated 2020 Jun 24]. Heart attack; [updated 2020 Jun 10; reviewed 2016 Aug 25; cited 2020 Jul 1]; [about 5 p.]. Available from: <https://medlineplus.gov/heartattack.html>

52. Brogden, R. N., et al. "Metoprolol: A Review of Its Pharmacological Properties and Therapeutic Efficacy in Hypertension and Angina Pectoris." *Drugs*, vol. 14, no. 5, Nov. 1977, pp. 321–48. DOI. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-197714050-00001>.
53. <https://pharmaguidances.com/phases-clinical-trials/>
54. <https://cdsco.gov.in/opencms/opencms/en/About-us/Functions/>
55. <https://globalhealthtrainingcentre.tghn.org/ich-good-clinical-practice/>
56. [New drug and clinical trail 2019 <https://www.raps.org/news-and-articles/news-articles/2019/7/indias-new-drugs-and-clinical-trials-rules-an-in>]
57. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK548069/adrNaranjo>.
58. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Metoprolol#section=Drug-and-Medication-Information>.
59. Kate, Sanika, Vishal Bodke, Ruchita Badekar, Paresh Bagul, Prajval Birajdar, and Pavankumar Dhoble. "Assessment and monitoring of adverse effect of ranitidine with pharmacovigilance study." (2023).DOI: 10.20959/wjpr202311-28841.
60. Gupta S K, Singh Surinder Textbook of Pharmacovigilance]
61. Kate, S., Bodke, V, Badekar, R., Bagul, P., Birajdar, P., & Dhoble, P. (2023). Assessment And Monitoring Of Adverse Effect Of Ranitidine With Pharmacovigilance Study.

54878478451240106

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

